

Spectrophotometric Studies of Complexing Equilibria of Zirconium with some Triphenylmethane Dyes

G. P. GUPTA and K. N. MUNSHI

Chemistry Department, Nagpur University Campus, Nagpur

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Spectrophotometric studies on the chelate formation between Zirconium and Chrome Azurol S, Solochrome Cyanine R, Eriochrome Azurol B and Pyrocatechol violet has been reported in different acid concentrations. All these ligands have been found to form two complexes in different acid concentration except Eriochrome Azurol B which forms only 2 : 1 complex. The study of these complexing reactions have been done in detail and the proper reaction equilibria suggested on the basis of number of protons released during complexation. The values of equilibrium constant of these complexes have also been evaluated.

THE present paper describes a detailed study on the nature of various complexing equilibria involved between zirconium and (a) 3-sulpho-2, 6-dichloro-hydroxy-dimethyl fuchsone dicarboxylic acid, sodium salt (Chrome Azurol S; abbr. CAS), (b) 2-sulpho-hydroxy dimethyl fuchsone dicarboxylic acid sodium salt (solochrome Cyanine R; abbr. SCR), (c) sodium salt of 2,6-dichloro hydroxy fuchsone dicarboxylic acid (Eriochrome Azurol B; abbr. EAB) and (d) pyrocatechol sulphonphthalein (Pyrocatechol violet, abbr. PCV). Much work on these ligands have been reported with different metal ions but the work on zirconium with CAS^{1,2}, SCR^{3,4} and PCV⁵⁻⁷ is scattered and often misleading. No work appears to have been reported on zirconium-EAB complex.

In the present paper an extensive study has been reported on the formation of different complexes of zirconium with these dyes and also the different complexing equilibria involved are discussed. Wherever possible the number of protons released during complexation have been experimentally found out and the Specic of zirconium participating, under a given set of conditions, is suggested.

Experimental

Apparatus : Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer with 1 cm glass cells has been used. An Elico pH-meter, model LI-10, have been used for pH measurements.

Reagents : Solution of zirconium oxychloride (E. Merck) was prepared by dissolving the sample in a calculated quantity of HCl in such a way that after dilution the stock solution becomes $10^{-3}M$ in 1.0M HCl. The zirconium content of this was estimated as pyrophosphate. Fresh solutions have always been used. Pure samples of CAS (Fluka), SCR (B. D. H.), EAB (Fluka) and PCV (B.D.H.) were further purified by converting them to their free acid and recrystallizing with 50% ethanol. The Purity (99.7%) was checked by titrating the free acid of these ligands, potentiometrically. A stock solution ($10^{-3}M$) was prepared by dissolving their known weight in NaOH solution and then adjusting its pH suitably.

Procedure : To maintain the acid concentration of metal solution to 0.1M or above, the calculated quantity of standard HCl was added or the stock solution is suitably diluted. pH-values above 1.0 was adjusted using pH-meter. The use of alkali is minimised to prevent the hydrolysis of zirconium. While preparing mixtures, zirconium solution was added to the ligand solution, the pH of both was preadjusted which was again checked and adjusted to proper pH value by pH-meter. Absorbance values are then recorded after 30 min. The range of final concentration of zirconium solution used was between 10^{-4} to $10^{-6}M$ where the chances of its polymerization is almost negligible.

Results and Discussion

Acid Dissociation Constants : The pK values of the ligands was determined by the method of Albert and Serjeant⁸ and the results obtained at room temperature (30°) are recorded below.

TABLE 1— pK VALUE OF THE LIGANDS

Ligands	$pK_1 \pm 0.02$	$pK_2 \pm 0.03$	$pK_3 \pm 0.05$
CAS	2.24	5.05	11.85
SCR	3.72	6.55	12.00
EAB	3.05	5.04	12.50
PCV	7.52	8.82	12.55

In case of SCR, CAS and PCV, the $-SO_3H$ group present might be dissociating at much lower pH and thus not permitting its determination under the present conditions of study.

Absorption spectra and composition of the chelates : Three series of solutions in different ratios of metal : ligand (1 : 1, 1 : 4 and 4 : 1) were prepared and the acid concentration of these solutions was adjusted from 1 molar HCl to pH 2.0 in all the cases with a pH difference of 0.5 units. The absorption spectra was then recorded in the entire visible range. pH values above 2.0 could not be adjusted due to the hydrolysis of zirconium. The results for 4 : 1 (Zr : ligand) ratio at different pH is recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF THE CHELATES

System	λ_{\max} (nm) at pH or in acid conc				
	1.0M HCl	0.5M HCl	0.1M HCl	pH 1.5	pH 2.0
Zr-CAS	470	490	550	550	500
Zr-SCR	490	510	510	540	540
Zr-EAB	ppt.	ppt.	470	470	530
Zr-PCV	550	550	550	550	600

The λ_{\max} of CAS, SCR and EAB alone, in the acid range of 1.0M to pH 2.0 is 470, 490 and 470 nm respectively. SCR however, shows a λ_{\max} of 550 nm in 1.0M to 0.5M HCl and 440 nm in 0.1M HCl to pH 2.0. These results and those mentioned in Table 2, suggest that in all the cases there is no evidence of complex formation in 1.0M HCl. SCR does not form complex with zirconium even in 0.5M HCl.

CAS appears to form two complexes with zirconium; one in 0.5M HCl having a λ_{\max} 490 nm (studied at 520 nm where the difference between the absorbance of complex and ligand alone is appreciable) and the other in 0.1M HCl having a λ_{\max} 550 nm. The composition as confirmed by the Job's method of continuous variations, mole ratio method and slope ratio method, comes out to 1 : 1 (in 0.5M HCl) and 1 : 2 (Zr : CAS, in 0.1M HCl).

A 1 : 1 complex has been confirmed to have formed in 0.5M HCl between Zr and SCR having a λ_{\max} 510 nm. However, a second chelate 2 : 1 (Zr : SCR) also forms from pH 1.5 to 2.0 having a λ_{\max} 540 nm and has been reported earlier by us⁹.

EAB precipitates out as free acid in 1.0 and 0.5M HCl as it has low solubility due to absence of $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ group. It however, forms a 2 : 1 (Zr : EAB) complex at pH 2.0 (λ_{\max} 530 nm) which is not very stable.

Two complexes have been found to form between PCV and Zr. The first complex forms in 0.1M HCl having a λ_{\max} 550nm (studied at 570 nm) with a composition 1 : 1. The other 2 : 1 (Zr : SCR) complex forms at pH 2.0 with a λ_{\max} 600 nm (studied at 620 nm).

All these ligands are multidentate and thus the probability of the polynuclear complex formation was checked by the straight line method of Asmus¹⁰. In all these systems, polynuclear complexes have not been found to form under the present conditions of study.

Study of Equilibrium : The nature of complexing equilibria involved between zirconium and CAS, SCR and PCV forming 1 : 1 complexes, in 0.5 to 0.1M HCl, may be discussed in general. The chances of hydrolysed specie of zirconium being present at this acid concentration is almost negligible particularly in presence of these ligands, and hence Zr^{4+} might be considered as the reacting specie. This is also confirmed by very fast reaction occurring between ligands and zirconium as the reaction at this acid concentration will be quite slow if hydrolysed specie of zirconium takes part in reaction. So, under these conditions assuming H_3A^-

($-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ group being dissociated much earlier) to be the ligands in 0.1 or 0.5M HCl (where A = CAS, SCR or PVC), the following general reactions may be written :

Reaction (a) holds good if the chelation occurs between a carboxylic group and phenolic group adjacent to it (between two adjacent phenolic groups in PCV) where as reaction (b) is possible if chelation occurs between carboxylic group (phenolic in case of PCV) and with adjacent quinonoid oxygen. These being the only two chelating positions in the above ligands and both give cationic chelates. The cationic nature is confirmed by the complete adsorption of these chelates on ion exchange resin Amberlite IR-120 (H) and also by electrophoresis experiment. Thus to find out the actual chelating reaction, the experiments were performed to find out the number of protons released during chelation. On the basis of dissociation constants of ligands if we assume that the reaction (a) may be the more probable one. We can then write the equilibrium constant K as :

$$K = \frac{[\text{Zr}(\text{HA})]^+}{[\text{Zr}^{4+}][\text{H}_3\text{A}^-]} \times [\text{H}^+]^2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(i)}$$

Now, the conditional stability constant, β may be written for reaction (a) as

$$\beta = \frac{[\text{Zr}(\text{HA})]^+}{[\text{Zr}^{4+}][\text{H}_3\text{A}^-]} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(ii)}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } K = \beta \times [\text{H}^+]^2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(iii)}$$

$$\text{or } \log \beta = -2 \log [\text{H}^+] + \log K \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(iv)}$$

A plot of $\log \beta$ vs. $\log [\text{H}^+]$ should thus be linear with slope equal to 2 and the intercept as equal to $\log K$.

The conditional stability constant of these complexes is evaluated at different acid concentrations, using a spectrophotometric method^{11,12}. The range of acid concentration is chosen in such a way that the absorbance of ligand remains constant at the wavelength of study. Equimolar mixtures of Zr and H_3A were prepared in known concentration of HCl. The solutions were then allowed to stand for an hour for complete equilibration and the absorbance values were then recorded at 520 nm (CAS), 510 (SCR) and 570 (PCV) nm. The extinction coefficients of ligand and complexes were also determined at the same wavelength.

Now if the total absorbance of the stoichiometric mixture is As , the molar extinction coefficient of the chelates and the ligand as Ec and Ea respectively, the initial and equilibrium concentration of Zr as A_T and A_e and that of ligand B_T and B_e respectively, the concentration of complex, can be determined as :

$$As = Ec \times Q + Ea \times B_e \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(v)}$$

$$= Ec \times Q + Ea (B_T - Q) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(vi)}$$

$$\text{hence } Q = \frac{As - EaB_T}{Ec - Ea} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(vii)}$$

Now, once the value of Q is known at a particular concentration, the value of conditional stability constant :

$$\beta = \frac{Q}{A_r \cdot B_c} \quad (\text{since } A_c = B_r) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(viii)}$$

$$\beta = \frac{Q}{(A_c)^2} = \frac{Q}{(A_T - Q)^2} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(ix)}$$

The values of $\log \beta$ are evaluated in this way at different acid concentrations and plotted against $\log [H^+]$ which gives a linear plot. The values of slope for Zr-CAS chelate (Fig. 1, curve A) comes out to be 2.1 whereas for Zr-SCR chelate (Fig. 1, curve B) it is 1.8. The slope, for Zr-PCV, chelate (Fig 2, curve A) comes out to be 2.2. Thus in all these cases, the values of slope is about 2.0, indicating the release of two protons during the reaction and hence the equation (a) holds good in these cases. The value of equilibrium constant ($\log K$) as obtained by the intercept of the curves comes out to be 3.49, 3.92 and 3.45 for the 1 : 1 zirconium chelates of CAS, SCR and PCV respectively.

FIG. 1 Relationship between $[H]^+$ and conditional stability constant (β) of CAS and SCR chelates of zirconium.
Curve A : $4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ Zr + CAS
Curve B : $4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ Zr + SCR

Equilibrium Study of 1 : 2 (Zr : CAS) complex :
The equilibrium study in 0.1M HCl, suggests the liberation of four protons during complexation reaction (Fig. 2 curve B, slope = 4.0). This is only possible if we assume the chelating positions to be the same as for 1 : 1 complex. Thus the following equilibrium reaction can be written.

This shows the complex to be anionic in nature which was confirmed by its complete adsorption on ion exchange resin Amberlite IR-45 (OH). The intercept as found (Fig. 2 curve B) is equal to 6.60 which is equal to the equilibrium constant for above reaction.

FIG. 2 Relationship between $[H]^+$ and conditional stability constant (β) of PCV and second CAS chelate of zirconium.
Curve A : $3.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ Zr + PCV
Curve B : $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ Zr⁴⁺ + $4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ CAS

It was not possible to study the equilibrium reaction of 2 : 1 chelates of EAB and PCV as the reaction at pH 2.0 involves the hydrolysed specie of zirconium and the range of pH within which the complex is stable is also very small. It may however be mentioned that the conditional stability constants of these chelates have been evaluated at pH 2.0 by the Job's method and mole ratio method. The average values are 9.90 ± 0.05 for 2 : 1 (Zr : EAB) chelate and 10.30 ± 0.05 for 2 : 1 (Zr : PCV) chelate at room temperature (30°).

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